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User Feedback of Apprentices on an Augmented Reality System for Learning from Errors in TVET

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Abstract

Context: The paper introduces an augmented reality learning system that detects human vocational actions in company-based dual TVET. Based on digital twins in a simulation environment, a head-mounted display visualises simulated consequences of detected action errors while the system prevents consequences in reality. The learning system enables situated learning in TVET. A prototype resulting from the development process shows potential as a suitable learning medium for vocational schools. Because vocational schools do not have situational vocational characteristics, the research question asks which technical adaptations apprentices suggest improving the prototype for vocational schools. Do their suggestions constitute situated learning characteristics?

Approach: 28 apprentices for Mechanics in plastics and rubber processing evaluated the prototype of the Augmented Reality learning system in a user study. The study used a learning task on an injection-moulding machine that assesses the quality and proceeds a filling study. The apprentices rated the system usability based on the ISONORM usability scale and responded to open feedback questions regarding possible improvements of the prototype.

Findings: The results indicate many objective situational characteristics and constraints that allow improvements of environmental and occupational characteristics at VET schools. Due to missing social interaction in the focused vocational learning tasks, the social and subjective dimensions have not been part of the study. A reflection and evaluation phase after completing the learning tasks needs to address this issue didactically for optimal competence acquisition.

Conclusion: The discussion paves the way for useful adaptations in order to incorporate an improved prototype in vocational schools. Teachers then can implement learning approaches based on vocational actions on a machine mock-up using an Augmented Reality learning system in the classroom. Future research should address the design of a suitable reflection phase to facilitate learning from performed actions.

Keywords: usability, learning media, digital twin, work-based

1 Introduction

Digitalisation plays an important role in the transformation processes of technical vocational education and training (TVET) all over Europe. European stakeholders stated numerous recommendations such as digital competence frameworks (Carretero et al., 2017; Redecker & Punie, 2017). According to that, TVET has to distinguish two phenomena of digital change. The first concerns vocational work processes due to the introduction of digital processes or tools (e.g. Goller et al., 2021). The second concerns the design of digitised learning and teaching processes (Dobricki et al., 2020) and is the focus of this contribution.

First, a theory chapter summarises the current state of the art of Augmented Reality learning media in TVET before presenting a current learning system development as subject of the study. A brief section introduces the technical point of view before formulating a research question combining both perspectives relying on experienced apprentices as experts in situational learning. Next, the methodology for the empirical investigation is outlined. Following the description of the results, they are discussed from several perspectives. Finally, a conclusion summarises the findings and gives suggestions for further research.

5.1 State of the Art: Augmented Reality Learning Media in TVET

In TVET, teaching and learning often utilise the opportunities of situated or work-based learning approaches (e.g. Lave & Wenger, 2011). Many current approaches in learning media development model learning situations in augmented (AR) or virtual reality (VR) (e.g. Aarkrog, 2021) and reduce situational attributes in a negative way from a perspective of situated learning due to increasing complexity (Teräs & Moreno Herrera, 2019). Thus, innovations should integrate digital learning technologies such as AR/VR in real learning situations to provide opportunities through their use (cf. Stender et al., 2021). When it comes to AR, engineering is an early adopter (Han et al., 2022) translating basic research into practice which offers great chances for TVET linked to engineering disciplines.

Simulation technology offers powerful options to implement TVET environments virtually for mobile or stationary learning process support (Bacca et al., 2015; Pürzel et al., 2013). Technical implementations of AR solutions in TVET to support learning, e.g. with a haptic tool simulator, are, for instance, found in carpentry (Jose et al., 2016) and plumbing (Jose et al., 2014) or, in the event technology industry in workplace training for rigging (Sommerauer, 2021). Another example from carpentry designs AR for three-dimensional drawings (Lee, 2020). Smith et al. (2021) simulate a fault diagnosis task of a three-phase power supply to enable guiding with AR comparable to the inspection and maintenance of an air compressor in a virtual cave simulating an engine plant room (Cheung & Sai Lok, 2016). Related to TVET, there is another system assisting in the motherboard assembly of computer hardware (Sirakaya & Kilic Cakmak, 2018) or supporting start-up operations of laboratory equipment (Alptekin & Temmen, 2018; Lester & Hofmann, 2020). One general learning media trend in AR is functional models within AR environments for TVET (Lavrentieva et al., 2019), e.g. a lathe (Güler & Yücedağ, 2018).

Welding is one domain where AR is a well-developed training solution (cf. Chan et al., 2022) that is currently becoming state of the art in many training centres worldwide (Lavrentieva, Arkhypov, Kuchma, & Uchitel, 2019). Usability and technology acceptance studies show positive results in this AR use case (Agrawal & Pillai, 2020; Okimoto et al., 2015; Papakostas et al., 2022). Yet there are still some objective situation characteristics of welding out of scope. However, fostering physiological and motor skills does not necessarily lead to experiences of typical welding situation characteristics that apprentices usually have to cope with. These include heat resulting from melting material, ultraviolet rays and counterforce of the electric arc, as well as current-carrying welding parts.

Referring to Zinn (2015), AR technology matches with the theory of situated learning. Situated learning states that learners co-participate in vocational tasks and learn by solving occupational problems (Billett, 1994; Lave & Wenger, 2011; Spöttl, 2008). In contrast to other didactics, it neglects content in order to investigate situational characteristics or constraints of learning and motivation effects, especially of higher-order transfer capabilities (Billett, 1994; Lave & Wenger, 2011). Therefore, learning processes attempt to support the interpretation of occupational situations for well-reflected vocational actions. Vocational action analyses imply no social interaction during work actions under consideration (Goppold et al., 2021a; Goppold et al., 2021b), which characterises multiple machine work as a standard work organisation in injection moulding. As a result, the main objectives in the first place are objective situational characteristics and constraints of vocational tasks and actions.

From a theoretical understanding, the technical system proposed in the following section provides a base for reflection to support a transfer by abstracting from situated experience toward universally applicable knowledge (cf. Tawfik et al., 2015).

5.2 Description of the Investigated Augmented Reality Learning System.

The researched Augmented Reality (AR) system detects and tracks actions in technical vocational work processes of apprentices with the help of digital twins that digitally map the structure and behaviour of the real learning environment (cf. Atanasyan et al., 2020). Furthermore, the system enables the simulation of vocational actions virtually in order to identify errors and prospective consequences (Schluse et al., 2018). A head-mounted display visualises hazardous error consequences to support learning processes (Cattaneo & Boldrini, 2017) while stopping potential negative incidents from occurring in the real world. Enhancing situated learning with a new dimension is the key benefit compared to traditional learning media, which contradicts the assistance paradigm of economic rationalisation (e.g. Wang et al., 2016). A systemic approach to a work system connects the interdisciplinary interfaces in the development process (Goppold et al., 2021c). Data logging on a cloud platform and the simulation allow virtually replaying actions to evaluate and reflect them in the light of various guiding ideas such as ecology (Rauner, 2013).

The didactical concept based on AR fosters competence acquisition in the work-based learning processes of company-based TVET (Goppold et al., 2021b). Furthermore, the same system could be a use case for vocational schools. It refers to vocational actions derived from activity theory and related occupational competence as normative guiding ideas in German VET curricula (e.g. Gessler & Howe, 2015).

Due to the technical complexity of two learning scenarios in injection moulding and CNC turning of company-based VET, the development team built multiple prototypes. The final prototype for the in-company application (see Figure 1) allows mimicking vocational learning tasks on an injection moulding machine mock-up that might have a second life as learning media in vocational schools.

Apprentices in the German dual VET system have expertise regarding work practice and situational constraints of work activity. This offers potential when involving them in learning media development. In addition to their feedback on the system entities such as AR glasses, apprentices counsel the development process regarding abilities to simulate practical work characteristics in school. The arising research question focuses on the optional continuing improvement of the final prototype as standalone learning media.

5.3 Usability

Usability is a multidimensional construct that describes the ability of a product to fulfil its purpose while used to perform a task effectively and efficiently under a certain condition (cf.

International Organization for Standardization, 2020). The products have to offer human-system interaction, and the construct gives valuable feedback to the product designers.

There is a formative and summative application of usability in the design processes of products and interaction with helpful recommendations on technical solutions of requirements in the product development. Mainly, studies deal with the design of human-computer interfaces and incorporate users in the early stages of development processes. Since the introduced AR learning system has a dual interface with AR glasses and the interface of the injection-moulding machine mock-up, usability evaluations by experienced apprentices will help to further develop the current prototype into an improved product for company-based TVET as well as a possible standalone school-based learning media. Usability questionnaires (Assila et al., 2016) provide a suitable standardised instrument to assess this construct in the study described in the following.

5.4 Research Question

Based on the considerations outlined above, the following leading research questions were formulated: Combining the TVET and technical perspective, which technical adaptations do apprentices of German dual TVET suggest in order to improve the AR learning media prototype for a stand-alone integration in school-based learning processes? Are these suggestions features of situated learning?

6 Methodology

To investigate the stipulated research questions, a user study was conducted. Apprentices from the dual VET system in Germany were the target group. Apprentices participating in the study had to perform an open learning task on quality assessment of a workpiece situated at an injection-moulding machine in order to evaluate quality concerning standards and customer demands. Furthermore, they had to reproduce the exact same workpiece using the prototype mock-up of a real injection-moulding machine.

Figure 1 shows a typical situation of the study in which apprentices needed to interact with the machine interface to optimise the production process of the injection-moulding machine. While working on these vocational tasks, participants wore a Microsoft HoloLens 2 as a head-mounted display that visualised details of the machine (e.g. a virtual representation of the machine tool) and situational feedback (e.g. results of an initiated automated measurement). Moreover, they used smart tools such as a scale to measure masses that provide the simulation with information on their technical vocational actions. The simulation visualised erroneous action consequences in AR without harmful and dangerous situations in reality.

The study utilised usability measures for the optimisation of the technical learning system. Due to a new usability standard (International Organization for Standardization, 2020), usability measurement instruments that match and satisfy the changed definitions of usability do not exist. Therefore, the short version of the ISONORM usability questionnaire (Prümper, 1997) was used, which comprises seven different scales with five items each on relevant topics for good usability referring to the previous standard definition (International Organization for Standardization, 2006).

Figure 1

Apprentice using the prototype of a technical learning system in the study

On top of the quantitative usability measures, the study obtained qualitative feedback in the form of recommendations for improvements in the questionnaire relying on apprentice experience in company-based learning processes with real machinery, as introduced at the end of section 1.2. An open question format was chosen to obtain additional information about their perceptions of the system. The procedure of the entire experiment is depicted in Figure 2.

The participants completed the online survey using an iPad with an attached keyboard after they finished the learning task. The task design, in combination with the linked surveys, resulted in a maximum test time of 90 minutes.

Figure 2

Procedure outline of the study. The part on the right addresses the research question described in the article.

7 Results

Participants in this study were 29 apprentices for Mechanics in plastics and rubber processing in their last year of apprenticeship, mostly from the injection-moulding sector. During the study, there was one drop-out while processing of the learning and work task, presumably due to motion sickness. However, there was no clearly attributable evidence of HMD use. This represents approximately 3 % of all German apprentices for Mechanics in plastics and rubber processing specialised in moulding in their last year and more than 10 % in the state of North Rhine-Westphalia (Bundesinstitut für Berufsbildung, 2022).

The sample included 25 men and three women participants. The average age is 22 years (SD 3.6). General education levels are six times on ISCED 344 and 22 times on ISCED 244. Additional reported vocational and academic education levels were stated four times on ISCED 454 and one time each on ISCED 747 as well as ISCED 254. 18 Participants worked with injection moulding machines on a daily basis, but only half of them worked with one of the manufacturers, Arburg, as presented in the study task. The sample predominantly had no relevant prior experience with AR glasses (n=23), AR via tablets or smartphones (n=20), and VR technology (n=15).

7.1 Usability Measures

Table 1 gives an overview of the usability results with all subscales of the questionnaire.

Table 1
Quantitative results of the ISONORM questionnaire

	n	M	SD	Cronbach's α
Overall Usability	28	37.9	4.2	0.60
Usability Suitability for the task	28	5.0	1.0	0.54
Usability Self-Descriptiveness	28	4.2	1.1	0.77
Usability Conformity with user expectations	28	4.8	1.0	0.62
Usability Suitability for learning	28	4.7	1.2	0.59
Usability Controllability	28	5.1	1.0	0.68
Usability Error tolerance	28	4.2	0.9	0.41
Usability Suitability for individualisation	28	5.0	0.8	0.66

While the average scores indicate good usability ratings for each of the scales, self-descriptiveness and error tolerance showed the lowest mean scores, thus indicating the most potential for improvements of the learning system in terms of usability. However, it must be pointed out that the reliability measure Cronbach's α varies for the usability subscales in the range from good for self-descriptiveness ($\alpha = 0.77$) to rejected reliability for error tolerance ($\alpha = 0.41$). Hence, the quantitative ratings should be interpreted with caution.

7.2 Qualitative Feedback of Apprentices on the Potential for Improvements

A qualitative content analysis was conducted with the answers to the open question that asked about improvement potential. Hereby, the answers were coded within an inductive categorisation system, and topic-based clusters were generated with reference to situational characteristics and constraints (cf. Mayring, 2015). The following text exemplifies all categories with some background information.

The data of the qualitative feedback provide convincing evidence that multiple issues exist with opportunities for improvements. The most frequently mentioned suggestion is that an assistance system function would be a good addition. This includes an option during task

processing to call up situation-appropriate information, such as material parameters, but also recommendations for (guided) actions.

Furthermore, the apprentices mentioned that they would like to have possibilities for action, which concerns both the extension of the learning task in the sense of a holistic filling study as well as further associated work actions such as a previous tool change.

In addition, some test persons noted a lack of acoustic feedback from the machine, which can provide a lot of information about the machining process. Moreover, several times there was a hint that the interaction possibility of the man-machine interface does not fully replicate the real machine, which, for example, includes dynamic updates of the temperatures of the screw heating.

Regarding the visualisations in the HMD, the feedback highlights improvements in the detail level, the use of video sequences, a higher frame rate and a better quality of the visualisations that clearly distinguishes from the environment. Some apprentices hoped for more action consequences in augmented reality, e.g. melting temperature visualisation or dynamic visualisations of more machine parts. One special recommendation suggests the visualisation of properties of the manufactured component as support instead of a separate self-guided determination. Individual feedback has still suggested to limit the duration of HMD use due to the high physical strain.

8 Discussion

8.1 Implications from Usability Incorporating Qualitative Aspects

Based on the usability results, self-descriptiveness also has some weaknesses that good documentation and help functions could fix. With these aids, apprentices would be able to start the HMD on their own without the required support of examiners.

However, related to Cronbach's alpha, there is low reliability for error tolerance. A possible explanation is a different definition of error in terms of usability and the present learning situation. Suitability for the task also indicates a diminished Cronbach alpha that might relate to missing functionalities of the man-machine interface when taking single items of the scale into account. The qualitative feedback argues in favour of the Arburg machinery experience of some participants who interact in different ways with the interface than the programmed one. Their negative ratings possibly add up to the measured effect.

Cut-offs of all subscales with alpha below 0.6 would lead to an incomplete overall usability measure as well as removing items from three-item scales because the problematic ones interfere in pairs. Therefore, the results deny any further discussions of these subscales and the overall usability due to low reliability.

8.2 Implications from Qualitative Feedback

Overall, the following recommendations for improvements should not hide the fact that the prototype also shows good interaction characteristics and high similarities in tool usage in the analysis phase of the learning task. With regard to the research question, the situated characteristics mentioned in the feedback address the following current disadvantages. The real injection-moulding machine offers a menu with sensor data logging that is demanded by some participants to gain insights into the machine state. A suitable simulation output could implement this missing feature with data derived from the properties of the digital machine twin and update them continually. Additionally, the machine menu for process parameter histories could improve the situated character of the learning task well, too. In particular, task individualisation is one advantage that could result from integrating the menu information into new learning tasks.

Other missing machine functions are incremental commands instead of auto-mode as well as linked visualisations of the machine states. When processing a filling study using this incremental workflow is a standard action that could not be part of the study due to its high time requirement, but should improve the prototype to mirror the real work tasks and behaviour. On top of that, dynamic visualisations of the tools and ejector pins can support the understanding of the tool because apprentices usually use the kinematics of a tool to comprehend its functions.

Furthermore, the requirement for acoustic and especially vibration feedback is a highly important recommendation that would lead to more situated learning scenarios. The apprentices and their trainers use these machine noise outputs to evaluate their function while running and derive states of different components from these information which is a classic feature of objective situatedness. This aligns with the demand for improved fitting of the augmented content into the environment. Accurate calibrations for the HMD and adapted colour grading might generate a better solution.

Finally, the apprentices found the system boundaries when addressing the need for further possible actions they usually process in workplace learning spaces. This is a well-known disadvantage of technical systems because they are only able to represent a predefined part of reality and do not cover, for example, the change of a tool in the machine. As a result, vocational situations have to be transferred into digital twins for simulations and modelling cannot represent their objectives holistically by definition.

8.3 Limitations

In interpreting the results, it should be taken into consideration that the used ISONORM questionnaire referred to a recently outdated standard and showed overall poor reliability. Hence, only partial results should be interpreted in combination with the results of the qualitative analysis. Another limitation that should be taken into consideration in the interpretation of the results concerns the focus on objective situation characteristics at the expense of subjective and social attributes. This is a legitimate weakness from a holistic understanding because the objective attributes derived from the results only describe situated learning in combination with subjective and social attributes. On the contrary, the results highlight the advantage of the learning task in detail and observing the action exactly without the previous planning phase and the evaluation with reflection afterwards. Hereby, the system yields a lot of information on event sequences of the action that need enrichments in social and subjective dimensions as well as the individual cognitive background. A reflection phase together with colleagues or trainers might be a solution. The objectiveness of technical action detection might point to a general flaw in using technical learning systems in the VET context.

9 Conclusion

Overall, the proposed Augmented Reality learning system and the prototype in the user study address a research gap on action-based learning systems in TVET incorporating learning from errors. The results and discussion show a pathway for adaptations to develop a standalone prototype for TVET schools enabling vocational actions on a machine mock-up using an Augmented Reality learning system. Apprentices commented on many details that point to missing objective situation characteristics of the mock-up as well as the augmented vocational situation compared to real work. The usability measurement revealed categories for technical improvements of the underlying simulation, especially the system improvement as well as the interaction with the HMD at start-up.

It should also be pointed out that situated learning always has a social and subjective dimension that was not considered in this study. Hence, these underrepresented dimensions should be the focus of ongoing and future research. Vocational actions using the prototype in

TVET schools might also support, for example, in evaluation and reflection phases addressing the impact of the performed actions and results on various guiding ideas.

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